

Strategic Leadership in Governance: Driving Accountability, Innovation, and Sustainable Futures

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Abstract

In this present era of rapid development, we are facing complex global issues like public health emergencies (COVID-19), climate change, socio-political instability and major development in scientific arena which are influencing governance. In order to address these problems, we require leaders who can think beyond their present administrative duties and responsibilities and take a strategic stance. Strategic leadership in governance guarantee sustainable development and institutional resilience by virtue of long-term vision and proactive decision making in alignment with the policies and societal values. The present paper was aimed to assess the role of strategic leadership in strengthening governance systems, accountability, innovation, collaboration and make an adaptive environment in institutions. In order to achieve the aforementioned objectives, meticulous literature review and conceptual analysis was carried out. The literatures were carried out from secondary data sources, policy frameworks and case studies. This review hence attempted to explore leadership theories and the practical application of strategic leadership to identify best practices and critical gaps. Our meticulous analysis from the literatures showed that strategic leadership enhances governance by embracing active stakeholder participation with support of ethical and moral values into decision making and developing common vision, mission and goals. Strategically foresighted leaders have the capacity to forecast upcoming dangers and also lead the team to adjust to the shifting conditions. Our analysis from the case study also demonstrated that an effective and foresighted leader support the advancement of creative policies, boost accountability, and lessen institutional inefficiencies. They also guarantee sustainability enhancing public confidence in governance frameworks. For a governance to be resilient and future oriented, there is a need of strategic leadership. By incorporating vision and accountability into the real-life practice in governance, a strategic leader can really transform the governance system.

Keywords: accountability, governance, innovation, strategic leadership